

Electrical conductivity of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in *n*-propanol at 25 °C

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Abstract : The conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate has been measured in *n*-propanol at 25 °C. The data were analyzed using the Fuoss-Onsager equation for 1 : 1 associated electrolytes and the characteristic function, Λ_0 (conductance at infinite dilution), d (contact distance) and K_A (association constant) has been derived. The association constant K_A was analyzed on the basis of the solvent separated-ion pair model.

Keywords : Conductivity, acetylcholine, association constant.

We have extensively studied the conductance behaviour of a number of acetylcholine salts in aqueous and various organic solvents¹. This paper presents a detailed study of conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in *n*-propanol at 25 °C under same conditions to compare the behaviour of these salts in simple solvents.

Results and discussion

The measured equivalent conductance are shown in Table 1. An approximate value of Λ_0 was estimated from Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ plot.

A more accurate value of Λ_0 was estimated from Fuoss-Kraus-Shedlovsky equation²,

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda S_{(z)}} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{(C\Lambda S_{(z)}F^2)}{K_D\Lambda_0^2}$$

where K_D is the dissociation constant and $S_{(z)}$ the Shedlovsky's function which was tabulated by Daggett for different values of z^3 . The value of z could be calculated from the following equation,

$$z = \frac{\alpha(C\Lambda)^2}{\Lambda_0^{3/2}}$$

in which α is the limiting tangent. The plot of $1/\Lambda S_{(z)}$ versus $(C\Lambda S_{(z)}F^2)$ gives $1/\Lambda_0$ as the intercept and $1/K_D\Lambda_0^2$ as the slope. Fig. 1 illustrates the (F.K.S.) plots for the studied salts.

The true values of Λ_0 , d and K_A were derived using Fuoss-Onsager equation⁴ and starting by the value of Λ_0 which was obtained from (F.K.S.) equation. In our calculations a computer program on an IBM-PC machine was used. The accuracies required in these computations are ± 0.02 for Λ_0 , ± 2 for $J < 200$; ± 5 for $J = 200 \rightarrow 1000$ and ± 10 for $J > 1000$.

Table 1. Conductance of acetylthiocholine salts in *n*-propanol at 25 °C

Acetylthiocholine chloride		Acetylthiocholine bromide		Acetylthiocholine iodide		Acetylthiocholine perchlorate	
10 ⁴ C ^a	Λ^b	10 ⁴ C	Λ	10 ⁴ C	Λ	10 ⁴ C	Λ
20.879	26.475	22.467	35.223	18.579	23.384	18.806	32.110
16.133	28.534	18.831	36.081	14.833	26.018	14.174	34.530
13.067	30.114	16.118	36.789	12.394	27.898	11.113	36.144
11.358	31.037	11.101	38.252	10.712	29.319	9.4007	37.256
9.8367	31.854	8.9141	38.962	9.6450	30.195	8.2702	37.975
8.7791	32.509	7.7323	39.427	8.6620	31.109	7.2704	38.743
7.8705	33.067	6.8822	39.768	7.7714	32.007	6.4835	39.364
7.2425	33.558	6.2824	40.000	7.0542	32.703	5.9138	39.653

^aequiv/L, ^b Ω^{-1} equiv⁻¹ cm².

Fig. 1. (F.K.S.) Plots for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in *n*-propanol at 25 °C.

Table 2. The characteristic parameters for acetylthiocholine salts in *n*-propanol at 25 °C

Salts	Λ^a	J	K_A	d (Å)	$\sigma\Lambda$
Ac.Th.Cl	46.959	3428.7	721.33	6.91	0.277
Ac.Th.Br	45.748	3433.2	132.26	6.49	0.095
Ac.Th.I	48.159	3094.6	1651.9	5.18	0.168
Ac.Th.ClO ₄	50.672	3097.6	492.81	4.71	0.267

^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$.

Fig. 2 shows the variation of d with J , from which the average value of d could be obtained by interpolation, through the knowledge of the average value of J . This value was obtained from the computer readings where J is being a function of d and has the following equation⁴,

$$J = \sigma_1 \Lambda_0 + \sigma_2$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 function of J .

The derived constants are represented in Table 2.

Table 2 reveals that Λ_0 increases from *s*-acetylthiocholine

Cl^- to ClO_4^- according to ionic equivalent conductance of anions. The values of J and d decrease with increasing the size of anions. This supports the opinion that for salts with common cation, the size of anion becomes the essential factor in controlling the extent of ion-pairing. The solvation of these anion of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate increases in the direction $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which is in accordance with the trend of d values. From the electrostatic point of view, since the distance between the cation and the anion increases in the same order, the forces of attraction increase in the order, $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$. In the present case the trend of K_A is irregularly increases with the increase of the size of anions. The gradual decrease of d with trend of K_A can be attributed

Table 3. Calculated values of K_2 and U for acetylthiocholine salts in *n*-propanol at 25 °C

Salts	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
Ac.Th.Cl	721.33	43.795	15.47	2.802
Ac.Th.Br	132.26	46.929	1.818	1.036
Ac.Th.I	1651.9	69.489	22.772	3.169
Ac.Th.ClO ₄	492.81	88.204	4.583	1.720

Fig. 2. Variation of J with \bar{a} in n -propanol at 25 °C.

to the relative position of the anion with respect to the cation which may not be completely spherical⁵.

El-Hammamy and Kawana⁶ studied the conductance of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in 2-propanol at 25 °C. They found the order of solvation, (\bar{a}) to be $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which is in agreement with the present work.

The same trend was found by Kawana⁷ for the conductance for s -acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in water at 25 °C.

Also El-Hammamy *et al.*, found the same trend for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in water at 25 °C. The same behaviour was for Co^{III} complexes of acetylpyridinethiosemicarbazone halides in methanol at 25 °C⁸.

In the present investigation the trend of \bar{a} revealed a good support to Sadek's conclusion in which \bar{a} represents the contact distance between the solvated ions and not the unsolvated ions as described by the original Fuoss statement⁹.

The irregular increase of K_A values with increasing size

of anions of s -acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate can be explained in the light of U term in the equation¹⁰,

$$\ln K_A = \ln \frac{4\pi N \bar{a}^3}{3000} + \frac{e^2}{\bar{a} D k T} + U$$

$$U = \frac{\Delta S}{k} - \frac{E_s}{k T}$$

where $\Delta S/k$ is the entropy/Boltzmann constant ratio which illustrates the probability of the orientation of solvent molecules around the free ions, and E_s/kT is an energy relationship which includes the energy of solvent molecules with respect to the two free ions and to the pair which they can form. The values of U term of s -acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate are given in Table 3. The result reveals that the value of U term decreases slightly from Cl^- to Br^- and it again decreases slightly from I^- to ClO_4^- , i.e. the ion-dipole interaction term entropy term $\Delta S/k$ is higher than the ion-dipole interaction term (E_s/kT) is more predominate than the entropy term.

The solvent separated ion-pair model is applied¹¹. In this

Table 4. Calculated values of the radii of ions for acetylthiocholine salts in n -propanol at 25 °C

Salts	Λ_0^a	$\lambda_0^- \eta^b$	λ_0^{+a}	λ_0^{+a}	Av. $-\lambda_0^{+a}$	R^{+c}	R^{-c}	$R^+ + R^{-c}$	\bar{a}^c
Ac.Th.Cl	46.956	0.20281	10.39	36.566			4.040	5.247	6.91
Ac.Th.Br	45.748	0.23561	12.07	33.678	34.774	1.207	3.478	4.685	6.49
Ac.Th.I	48.159	0.26137	13.39	34.769	± 0.9		3.135	4.342	5.18
Ac.Th. ClO_4	50.672	0.32228	16.51	34.062			2.543	3.750	4.71

^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, ^b $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{P}$, ^c Å .

model a multiple-step association occurs, i.e. solvent separated-ion pair can be illustrated in the following scheme :

The association constant is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_A = K\Sigma &= \frac{[C_{(\text{ion-pair})}]}{[C_{(\text{acetylthiocholine})^+}] [C_{X^-(\text{solvent})_n}]} \\
 &= K_1 (1 + K_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

where, $K\Sigma = K_A$ is obtained from conductance measurements,

$$K_1 = 4 \pi N \bar{a}^3 / 3000 e^b$$

K_2 was thus calculated. The results compiled in Table 3, indicate that K_1 increases from Cl^- to ClO_4^- , i.e. the ion-pair prefers the more solvated form (case I) than the desolvated form (case II).

Radii of ions :

The electrostatic radii R^+ and R^- are given by equation

$$R^\pm = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda_0^\pm \eta_0$$

In the present case λ_0^- values were obtained from the intercept of the straight lines resulting from the plots of Walden products $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ versus the reciprocal of the molecular weight as previously discussed¹. To calculate λ_0^+ for (*s*-acetylthiocholine)⁺, the average value obtained for λ_0^+ in case of the Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and ClO_4^- was used in calculations. Applying Stoke's equation, one may obtain the values of both R^+ and R^- . These data are recorded in Table 4. It can be seen from Table 4 that the values of \bar{a} are greater than the electrostatic radii ($R^+ + R^-$) which obtained from Stoke's equation. This is due to the solvation of ions¹¹.

Experimental

n-Propanol, *s*-acetylthiocholine chloride, bromide, iodide and perchlorate were purified as reported elsewhere⁷. The specific conductance for purified *n*-propanol was found to be

($2.3\text{--}4.8 \times 10^{-8}$) $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. The density of *n*-propanol was determined using a 20 mL pycnometer at 25 ± 0.02 °C and was found to be 0.79960 g/cm³. Its viscosity was measured at 25 °C using a modified Ubelöhde suspended level viscometer with a flow-time of 172.4 s for water. It was found to be 1.952 cp. The dielectric constant value was used as reported in the literature. All solutions were prepared by weight reduced to vacuo. Salts weighed by difference on microbalance which read to ± 0.1 mg. Dilution was carried out successively into the cell by siphoning the solvent by means of dispenser. An Erlenmeyer cell with bright platinum electrodes was used. The cell constant was calculated ($0.05443 \pm 0.43\%$ cm⁻¹) using the Lind-Zwolenik-Fuoss¹² equation.

A "Pye" 11700 conductance bridge was used for measuring the resistance of solutions at 5 Kc/s.

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